

Microplastics removal from urban WWTP through microfiltration

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Abstract

The production of reclaimed water for aquifer recharge or upstream discharge has gained interest as an alternative to tackle increasing hydric stress worldwide. In line with the European Reused Water Regulation 2020/741, which anticipates microplastics (MPs) regulation by 2028, this work aims to assess the effectiveness and the operational performance of three microfiltration membranes -with different spacer thickness and shapes- for the removal of microplastics within a wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) to avoid their release into water bodies. Sampling points upstream (i.e. Pretreatment effluent) and downstream (i.e. WWTP effluent) from a WWTP were used to assess whether the microfiltration should be used as an intermediate treatment or as a polishing technology. Results showed that although microfiltration membranes were capable to effectively reject microplastics, the permeate flux reduction was significantly lower when it is used as polishing technology, thus enlarging the membrane element lifespan. In addition, the membrane with corrugated spacer (V0.2-5CB-1812F) showed the best performance in terms of initial flux and flux reduction along the filtration experiments. This work highlights the feasibility of using microfiltration for the prevention of microplastics release into water bodies from WWTP, but further studies are needed to assess the long-term performance of the membrane elements.

Keywords

Microfiltration, microplastics, wastewater treatment plant, water reuse

INTRODUCTION

Hydric stress, both droughts and floods, is an increasing global concern, that has raised the need of new water management strategies. In this context, the production of reclaimed water from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) for aquifer recharge or upstream discharge, among others, has gained interest to assure sustainable water supply. However, this practice introduces challenges, particularly due to the presence of contaminants of emerging concern such as microplastics (MPs), which could pose risks to human ecosystems health. In fact, the European Reused Water Regulation 2020/741 emphasises the need to monitor closely the MPs content in reclaimed water.

Pressure-driven membrane processes are well-known options for effective contaminant removal and they are increasingly considered for novel industrial applications such as MPs removal (Kumar Dey et al., 2025). Microfiltration (MF) seems to be a promising option due to the suitable pore size range of MF membranes for MPs rejection, allowing efficient large-volume treatment. While the role of spacers in membrane filtration for solid removal is well-established, the effects of different geometries (i.e. corrugated and parallel shapes) and thickness on MPs retention are still underexplored (Luogo et al., 2022; Takeuchi et al., 2023).

This study aims to assess different strategies for the efficient removal of MPs from WWTP effluents to avoid their release into water bodies. 5 different points from a WWTP were firstly sampled to find the most suitable location for locating the MF and, afterward, the performance of 3 MF membranes with different spacer geometries and thickness were assessed for MPs removal.

MATERIALS & METHOD

Three MF membranes with 0.20 μm pore size were tested: (1) 80 mil corrugated spacer (V0.2-5CB-1812F coded as C-80, Synder, USA), (2) 46 mil diamond-shaped spacer (V0.2-3B-1812F coded as D-46, Synder, USA), and (3) 31 mil diamond-shaped spacer (1812-MV020-31 coded as D-31, MANN+HUMMEL, Germany). Their performance was evaluated using a crossflow filtration system SW-18 (MMSX, Switzerland), operating in batch mode.

Wastewater from La Almozara WWTP located in Zaragoza (Spain) was treated by recirculating by circulating samples at a flow rate of 900 L h⁻¹ and a trans membrane pressure of 1.5 bars, until a recovery rate of 80%. The experiments were performed at room temperature (25°C), and the membranes were weighed before and after the filtration process to measure MP retention within the membrane element. To standardise the weighing process, membranes were submerged in distilled water before and after filtration and allowed to drain for one hour.

From each filtration, samples of permeate and retentate were collected for MPs quantification by weight and by particles counting. For MPs weighting, the samples were filtered under vacuum, dried in an oven at 105°C for one hour, and finally weighed. For MPs counting, a Fenton process was firstly used for organic matter oxidation in the retentate streams. by adjusting the pH to 2.80 with H₂SO₄ and mixing FeSO₄·7H₂O and H₂O₂. The oxidised retentate and MF permeate were saturated with sodium chloride to enhance density and promote microplastic flotation. Afterwards, supernatant was filtered under vacuum using glass fibre filters for MPs retention. Filters were then stained with rhodamine B and observed under a UV microscope to quantify MP particles.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

In this study, five different streams of La Almozara WWTP were characterised (Table 1), and two points were selected for the implementation of the MF process.

Table 1. WWTP selected streams physic-chemical characterisation's average.

Parameter	Raw	Pretreatment	Primary settle	Biologic treatment	WWTP effluent
pH	8.09	7.89	7.60	7.18	7.79
EC ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)	1546.00	1628.00	1663.00	1605.00	1633.00
COD (mg L^{-1})	504.00	560.00	337.00	2762.00	37.30
Microplastics (MPs L ⁻¹)*	1380.00	9360.00	1980.00	1304.00	806.00
TSS (g L^{-1})	0.19	0.21	0.11	2.04	0.01

*As a number of particles within a 1 L sample.

As can be observed in Table 1, although TSS content is similar between raw wastewater and pretreatment effluent, the content of MPs is significantly higher in pretreatment effluent, probably due to the breakdown of larger particles when passing through the coarse and fine screens.

After primary settling and biological treatment, the WWTP effluent showed the lowest TSS, COD, and MPs concentration. the results suggest MF is most appropriate to be trialled for removal of microplastics for either pre-treatment or WWTP effluent stages. Removing MPs from pretreatment effluent avoids their presence in subsequent treatment steps, thus obtaining a MPs reduced effluent. By contrast, MF can be also used as a polishing step for WWTP effluent to avoid its release into water bodies.

The performance of the different membranes in terms of flux evolution throughout the filtration experiments is shown in Figure 1. It can be observed different behaviour for both streams as diamond-shaped spacers showed better performance, in terms of permeate flux, for pretreatment effluent although D-31 reported significant flux reduction during the filtration; while corrugated spacers

showed better performance -both in terms of initial flux and flux reduction- when treating WWTP effluents. The greater flux reduction as well as the lower initial flux during pretreatment effluent filtration indicates a higher membrane fouling caused by the high solid content.

Figure 1. MF performance for the three selected membranes in the pretreatment stream (left) and WWTP effluent stream (right).

In terms of MP rejection (Table 2), C-80 reported the highest rejection capacity for both streams, while D-31 and D-46 reported similar results. In addition, it is important to note that despite WWTP effluent containing fewer MPs, they were of smaller size with greater presence of fibres that can easier permeate the membrane, resulting in lower MP rejection rates when treating WWTP effluent compared with pretreatment effluent.

Table 2. Microplastic's average quantification for the two studied streams.

Parameter		D-46	C-80	D-31
		Pretreatment effluent		
Retentate	Fragments (MPs L ⁻¹)	6384	6768	5240
	Fibres (MPs L ⁻¹)	1260	1456	1620
Permeate	Fragments (MPs L ⁻¹)	8	4	4
	Fibres (MPs L ⁻¹)	816	699	940
		WWTP effluent		
Retentate	Fragments (MPs L ⁻¹)	1616	2096	928
	Fibres (MPs L ⁻¹)	552	552	512
Permeate	Fragments (MPs L ⁻¹)	0	0	0
	Fibres (MPs L ⁻¹)	440	464	520

These results can aid in the decision-making process for implementing this technology in a real environment. In this case, placing the MF system as WWTP effluent polishing appears to be the most efficient approach as it accomplishes the goal of significantly reducing MPs release into water bodies while reporting lower membrane fouling, thus enlarging membrane lifespan. Regarding MF membrane performance, C-80 showed better performance both in terms of permeate flux (with a flux stabilisation at an early stage of the filtration process) and MPs rejection. However, before its deployment at industrial scale, further studies are needed for assessing the C-80 MF performance in long-term uses.

CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluates the potential for implementing a MF system to avoid MPs release into water bodies within a WWTP as an intermediate treatment -treating pretreatment effluent- and as a polishing strategy -treating WWTP effluent-.

Results showed that the use of MF as a polishing step would allow for effective MPs removal while increasing membrane lifespan compared with its use as an intermediate treatment. Moreover, C-80 membrane showed better performance both in terms of flux stability and MP retention, showcasing those membranes with higher spacer thickness and corrugated geometry as a promising option for the removal of solids from liquid streams.

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